

Heat Transfer Analysis on MHD Hybrid Nanofluid Flow Over a Stretching Surface in a Porous Medium Under the Influence of Thermal Radiation

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Abstract

The new era of technology in the field of fluids, hybrid nanofluid due to its thermal properties has become an interesting topic among researchers. In enhancing the heat transfer rate compared to nanofluid which gives better result. In this paper we investigate the significant effects of magnetic field over a stretching surface containing aluminium oxide and cobalt hybrid nanofluid with base fluid Engine oil in a porous medium under the influence of thermal radiation is investigated. In this paper, we used Engine oil mixed with Alumina Oxide (Al_2O_3) and Cobalt (Co) as the nanoparticles. The set of PDEs are constructed for the fluid flow and transformed to a set of ODEs by using the suitable self-similarity variables and hence solved numerically using Bvp5c scheme in MATLAB. In this we study how the operational factors affect fluid flow efficiency. The Effects of magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) and relevant thermophysical properties on velocity and temperature profile, skin friction (C_f) and Nusselt number (Nu) are thoroughly examined and presented graphically. It is noted that, for the larger values of the porous parameter the skin friction slowly increases and for rate of heat transfer the Nu profile enhanced, for the increasing in M and Rd . Further, it is noted that compared to nanofluid the hybrid nanofluid possess better result.

Keywords: MHD, Hybrid nanofluid, Thermal radiation, Porous medium, heat transfer.

I. Introduction

A crucial stage in the process of centrally heating or cooling an object is the transfer of heat from one place to another. For a device or system to operate at its best, the significant heat it generates needs to be lowered to a manageable level or dispersed. To reduce the amount of heat on devices like in industries, including electronics and the automotive industry, fluid refrigerants have long been used. Nevertheless, the heat transmission of conventional liquid refrigerants have a weak heat transfer [1],[2]. Due to this there is a greater potential for creativity and technological advancement in the field of cooling [3]. One of the methods used to increase the effectiveness of heat transfer in liquid refrigeration systems is the use of nanofluid, which is a fluid containing nanoparticles [4]. The problem with fluid that has scattered nanoparticles is that it can coagulate, deposit, and clog flow lines [5]. One potential solution to the above problems is to use nanomaterials implanted as microparticles. The semiconductor, automotive, power, and universal healthcare industries, among others, use nanofluids widely because of their enticing high-temperature, visual, and electromagnetic properties [6],[7].

To improve thermal efficiency, an innovative method of combining two or three different types of metallic nanoparticles with the base fluid has been developed [8]. Metallic nanoparticles are mixed with a base fluid in a hybrid nanofluid. Heat transmission is improved when machines are heated or cooled using hybrid nanofluids [9]. A lot of study has been done on the combinations of nanoparticles in base fluids to produce a refrigerant with higher thermal conductivity. Particle diameter, volume fraction, thermal efficiency, and viscosity affect the hybrid nanofluids temperature distribution and heat capacity [10]. Nanofluid is a great refrigerant that also increases material impact energy. Alumina is a metal that is frequently utilized in the study of hybrid nanofluids because of its higher mechanical power and chemical stability when compared to other metals. Different types of cobalt alloys are used in high-hardness devices like jet turbines. Cobalt metal is occasionally used for electroplating due to its superior standards, high hardness, and superior corrosion resistance.

The study of fluids in a magnetic field with accompanying electric currents is known as magnetohydrodynamics or MHD. Magneto-fluid dynamics is the name given to this mechanism. Liquid crystals, ions, plasmas, and seawater are a few examples of magneto-fluids. Hannes Alfvén received the 1970 Nobel Prize in Physics in recognition of his groundbreaking work in the field of MHD. The magneto-nanofluid is a material that combines the properties of liquids and magnets into a single substance. The heat transport is altered by the magnetic effects in addition to radicalizing the particles in the liquid system [11],[12]. Furthermore, the absorption is reconstructed due to the magnetic effects. Compared to non-malignant nanoparticles, they have a higher concentration of viscous bodily cells, and the cells enhance blood circulation. Also in the

biomedical industry magnetic nanoparticles are used. Astronomy, medicine, metal processing, optical grafts, geophysical fields, and petrochemical engineering have all given MHD a great deal of attention [13],[14].

Power turbines, motor engines, and other devices including automobiles all require engine oil. In mechanical systems, contact between shifting gears diminishes efficiency by heating dynamic energy. The main purpose of oil is to reduce contact between moving parts. Contacting parts may be cooled by the engine oil. Mechanical cooling and lubrication depend on heat transfer and engine oil thickness. Viscosity affects oil circulation and pumping force. This study also takes aluminum oxide and cobalt into account. Because cobalt-based wonderful alloys remain immovability at high temperatures, they are recycled in jet machines, including military combat planes. Al_2O_3 is an excellent ceramic oxide with many applications, including aerospace manufacturing and other high-modernization fields [15], [16].

Analyzing the idea of magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) across a stretching surface in the presence of a porous media and linear heat radiation has not been done, according to the literature currently in publication. PDEs are the form that the constructed equations take. A self-similarity transformation is applied to transform the PDE into ODEs and we used Bvp5c for the graphical representation. In this work, we use hybrid nanofluids comprising aluminum oxide and cobalt as well as engine oil as the basis fluid. This model makes a substantial contribution to the domains of nuclear reactor cooling, automotive engineering, and aviation technology. The section under "The results and discussion" contains the graphs that show the various effects of physical significance.

II. Mathematical model

A two-dimensional heat transfer representation in a mixed-heat-dispersal (MHD) aluminum oxide–cobalt hybrid nanofluid is investigated in addition to a stretched surface. Thermal radiation is considered in the context of the energy and temperature equation. Two different types of nanoparticles, Al_2O_3 and cobalt are suspended in the base fluid engine oil, as Table 1 illustrates. The velocity is expressed as $u_w = ax$. The velocity components both u and v are measured along the x –axis and y –axis, respectively. Moreover, the symbols T_w and T_∞ , which are shown in Figure 1, respectively, represent the temperature of the sheet and the temperature of the free stream.

Table 1. Numerical values for Thermophysical properties of base fluid Engine oil, Al_2O_3 -Cobalt hybrid nanofluid [17].

Property	Engine oil	Al_2O_3	Cobalt
Density ρ (kgm^{-3})	863	3970	8900
Specific heat C_p ($Jkg^{-1}K^{-1}$)	2048	765	420
Heat conductivity k_f ($Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$)	0.1404	40	100
Electrical conductivity σ (Ωm) ⁻¹	55×10^{-6}	1.602×10^7	1.602×10^7
Pr	6450		

Fig.1 Flow geometry of the problem

The governing equations for the flow are constructed as [15], [16].

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\rho_{hnf}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\rho_{hnf}} \frac{u}{K^*} - \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\rho_{hnf}} (B^2 u), \quad (2)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{k_{hnf}}{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{1}{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}} \left(\frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\sigma_{hnf} B^2}{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}} u^2. \quad (3)$$

Then by Rosseland approach, we have

$$q_r = -\frac{4\sigma^*}{3k^*} \frac{\partial T^4}{\partial y}. \quad (4)$$

Now by using the Taylor's series expansion of T^4 about T_∞ and neglecting terms having higher order, we now obtain

$$T^4 = 4T_\infty^3 T - 3T_\infty^4. \quad (5)$$

Substituting Eq. (5) in Eq. (3), we obtain

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{k_{hnf}}{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{1}{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}} \frac{16T_\infty^3}{3k^*} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\sigma_{hnf} B^2}{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}} u^2. \quad (6)$$

Then the corresponding boundary conditions are as follows:

$$u = u_w(x) = cx, v = 0, k_{hnf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = h_f (T_f - T), \quad \text{at } y = 0$$

$$u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_\infty \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow \infty. \quad (7)$$

The following suitable self-similarity transformations are defined as:

$$u = cxf'(\eta), v = -\sqrt{cv_f} f(\eta), \theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_f - T_\infty}, \eta = y \sqrt{\frac{c}{\nu_f}}. \quad (8)$$

Thermophysical properties of hnf are

$$H_1 = \frac{\mu_{hnf}}{\mu_f}, H_2 = \frac{\rho_{hnf}}{\rho_f}, H_3 = \frac{(\rho c_p)_{hnf}}{(\rho c_p)_f}, H_4 = \frac{k_{hnf}}{k_f}, H_5 = \frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_f}.$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 H_1 &= \frac{1}{(1-\phi_1)^{2.5} (1-\phi_2)^{2.5}}, \\
 H_2 &= \left\{ (1-\phi_2) \left[(1-\phi_1) + \phi_1 \left(\frac{\rho_{s_1}}{\rho_f} \right) \right] + \phi_2 \frac{\rho_{s_2}}{\rho_f} \right\}, \\
 H_3 &= (1-\phi_2) \left[(1-\phi_1) + \phi_1 \left(\frac{(\rho c_p)_{s_1}}{(\rho c_p)_f} \right) \right] + \phi_2 \frac{(\rho c_p)_{s_2}}{(\rho c_p)_f}, \\
 H_4 &= \frac{k_{s_1} + 2k_{bf} - 2\phi_2(k_{bf} - k_{s_2})}{k_{s_2} + 2k_{bf} + \phi_2(k_{bf} - k_{s_2})} \times \frac{k_{s_1} + 2k_f - 2\phi_1(k_f - k_{s_1})}{k_{s_1} + 2k_f + \phi_1(k_f - k_{s_1})}, \\
 H_5 &= \frac{\sigma_{s_2} + 2\sigma_{nf} - 2\phi_2(\sigma_{nf} - \sigma_{s_2})}{\sigma_{s_2} + 2\sigma_{nf} + \phi_2(\sigma_{nf} - \sigma_{s_2})} \times \frac{\sigma_{s_1} + 2\sigma_f - 2\phi_1(\sigma_f - \sigma_{s_1})}{\sigma_{s_1} + 2\sigma_f + \phi_1(\sigma_f - \sigma_{s_1})}.
 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Using the ideal approach given in Eq (8), Eqs. (2) and (6) are translated to get the following dimensionless ODEs.

$$\frac{H_1}{H_2} f''' + H_2 (ff''' - (f')^2) - \frac{H_1}{H_2} Kf' - \frac{H_5}{H_2} Mf' = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$\theta'' \left(H_4 + \frac{4}{3} Rd \right) + H_3 Prf\theta' + \frac{H_5}{H_3} MEc (f')^2 = 0. \quad (11)$$

The boundaries of the change are described as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(0) &= 0, f'(0) = 1, H_4 \theta'(0) = -Bi(1 - \theta(0)) \\
 f'(\infty) &= 0, \theta'(\infty) = 0.
 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$M = \frac{\sigma_f B^2}{\rho_f a}$ is the Magnetic field parameter	$p_r = \frac{\mu_f (c_p)_f}{k_f}$ is the Prandtl number
$Rd = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{k^* k_f}$ is the Radiation parameter	$K = \frac{\nu_f}{aK^*}$ is the Porosity parameter
$Ec = \frac{a^2 x^2}{c_p (T_f - T_\infty)}$ is the Eckert number	$B_i = \frac{h_f}{k_f} \sqrt{\frac{\nu_f}{a}}$ is the Biot number

The dimensional form of skin-friction coefficient, C_f and Nusselt number Nu are expressed as

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho_f u_w^2} \quad (13)$$

Where shear stress τ_w is $\tau_w = \mu_{mf} \left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0}$

$$Nu = \frac{xq_w}{k_f(T_w - T_\infty)} \quad (14)$$

Where heat flux q_w is $q_w = -k_{hnf} \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0}$

The non-dimensional form of equations (13) and (14) converted as

$$Re_r^{\frac{1}{2}} C_f = Cf = H_1 f''(0), \quad (15)$$

$$Re_r^{\frac{1}{2}} Nu_r = Nu = -H_4 \theta'(0). \quad (16)$$

Here Re_r is the local Reynolds number.

III. Numerical scheme

Simply enter numbers into the Bvp5c scheme in MATLAB to solve the nonlinear ODE system of Equations (10)-(11) along with the boundary conditions (12). Initially, Eqs.(10)-(12) are changed as a set of first-order equations. So that Bvp5c can be used in the MATLAB solver. In the current study for a different vales of the parameters are taken and the numerical results are presented.

Fig.(2). Flow chart of the present investigation problem.

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By using BVP5c technique, the non-dimensional controlling flow model (10)–(11), which are subject to the boundary conditions (12), and solved numerically. We evaluated using the non-dimensional parameter values. Table 2, which illustrates the variations in skin friction coefficient, yields the exact solutions. It was concluded that the results of the two studies were reasonably accurate. The numerical procedure for the BVP5c approach is displayed in Figure 2.

Table 2: comparison table for various values of Prandtl numbers.

Pr	Ali et al.[15]	Present results
0.7	0.4560	0.45532
2.0	0.9113	0.91032
7.0	1.8954	1.89562

Fig.(3) shows how M affects the velocity sketch. The velocity profile shows a declining tendency for higher M values, which suggests that M is becoming more valuable. Physically speaking, a rise in M results in the production of a Lorentz force, which slows the liquid's flow. The increased resistance that results from the Lorentz force's antagonistic relationship with fluid motion causes the flow velocity to decrease, which in turn causes to drop the velocity field. Raising the K values makes a porous substance physically more difficult to flow across. This is seen in Fig.(4) when the velocity outline is improved by doing so. As seen in Figure 4, increasing the K values physically makes a porous material harder to pass through, slowing the flow of fluids. This has the immediate and direct effect of reducing the outermost boundary layer's dimension.

Fig. (3). variation of M on $f'(\eta)$.

Fig. (4). variation of K on $f'(\eta)$.

Fig.(5). illustrates how the magnetic field affects the temperature profile. It says that the energy contour grew as the M parameter increased. This improvement results from the resistive Lorentz force that is created when a M is added to an electrically conducting material. The fluid's temperature can be raised by this kind of force. Thus, the temperature profile improves for this reason. The radiation parameter temperature profile features are displayed in Fig.(6). Thermal radiation is the radiant energy emitted by all generators above zero, in terms of physics. Atoms in matter rotate due to electromagnetic radiation from hot surfaces, producing kinetic energy. The graph shows how heat transport is improved by increased radiation. The thermal barrier is strengthened as R_d is raised because more heat is transferred into the liquid. Temperature rises in response to radiation growth because the mean absorption coefficient decreases.

Fig.(5). variation of M on $\theta(\eta)$.

Fig.(6). variation of Rd on $\theta(\eta)$

Fig.(7). variation of Ec on $\theta(\eta)$.

Fig.(8). variation of Pr on $\theta(\eta)$.

Fig.(9). Sway of K and M on Cf

Fig.(10). Sway of Rd and M on Nu

Fig.(11). Sway of K and M on C_f .

Fig.(12). Sway of M and Rd on Nu .

Fig.(13). Stream lines for $M = 0.5$.

Fig.(14). Stream lines for $M = 1.0$.

Fig.(7) illustrates how the Eckert number affects the energy profile. It claims that rising Ec values correspond to rising temperature contours. Ec physically produces the frictional forces that raise the temperature of the fluid. Fig.(8) shows the impact of Pr on energy profile. It claims that the temperature outline is improved by raising the Pr values. The liquid's thermal dissipation basically decreases, which lowers the temperature outline. From Fig.(9) and (10), it displays the influence of the K and M on the C_f . It demonstrates that when K and M increase, the skin friction factor decreases, in contrast to Fig.(11), which exhibits the opposite trend. The Nu profile's inspiration from the Rd and magnetic field is illustrated in Fig.(10) and (12). It demonstrates that in any situation where the Rd and magnetic field are larger, the Nu is increasing. The magnetic parameter is shown for different values of $M = 0.5, 1.0$ affects on streamlines plots in Fig.(13) and (14). Electrical conductivity molecules are drawn closer to the main stream by the strength of the magnetic parameter.

CONCLUSIONS

In the current work, the numerical solution for the MHD of a hybrid nanofluid of engine oil and cobalt across a stretching surface was investigated. The temperature and velocity problems were resolved using the numerical method (BVP5c), and the result was a true solution to the model. Numerous graphical representations of the results are provided, such as streamlines, two-dimensional plots, and three-dimensional surface plots.

Many intriguing findings were obtained from the investigation, some of which are mentioned below:

- ✧ The velocity profile decreases when the porosity parameter and magnetic field values increases.
- ✧ The radiation parameter improved, when the temperature profile enhanced.

- ✧ For larger porosity parameter values the skin friction factor gradually increased.
- ✧ The Nu profile was improved due to the rising M and Rd values.
- ✧ Streamlines are characterized by oscillation, which is necessary to increase the magnetic field parameter.

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